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e-ABSTRACT BOOK

EVALUATION OF pH EFFECT ON THE REMOVAL OF PESTICIDES FROM WATER USING NANOFILTRATION MEMBRANE

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Pesticides are mainly used in order to maintain food production and raw material supply due to a constant population growth. However, persistency and excessive use of pesticides in the agricultural domain has raised an issue of the potential harmful effects of pesticides on the environment. Pesticides are often detected in various water sources and, therefore, their efficient removal from water is required. The aim of this study was to determine efficiency of a nanofiltration membrane in the removal of malathion (insecticide) and propiconazole (fungicide) at three pH values. Experiments were conducted in a METCell dead-end stirred cell unit from Evonik Industries AG (Germany). High pressure nitrogen gas cylinder was used for obtaining 3 bar pressure in the system. Nanofiltration membrane, NF270 (FilmTec™), with molecular weight cut off 400 Da was used for the removal of two pesticides at pH 4, pH 7 and pH 10. Apparent 100% rejection was obtained for propiconazole with the NF270 membrane at all tested pH values. However, malathion rejection using nanofiltration membrane decreased from 100% to 87.54% at pH 4 and pH 7, respectively. Additionally, malathion was not detected in sample solutions, including feed, permeate and retentate, at pH 10. Molecular weight of malathion and propiconazole is 330.36 Da and 342.22 Da, respectively, however dissociation constant (pKa value) of malathion and propiconazole is 6.8 and 1.09, respectively. Neutral charge of malathion at pH 7 could cause lower rejection of malathion at pH 7 compared to pH 4, due to absence of electrostatic interactions. Degradation of malathion increases with an increase in pH value and, therefore, malathion was not detected in sample solutions at pH 10 due to intense hydrolysis. Size exclusion and electrostatic interactions have an evident role in the removal of pesticides from water with nanofiltration membranes.

Keywords: nanofiltration, water treatment, pesticides, malathion, propiconazole

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